

Review

Impacts of agronomic measures on crop, soil, and environmental indicators: A review and synthesis of meta-analysis

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable agricultural management implies optimization of resources for crop production while minimizing adverse impacts on the environment. This requires a better understanding of the synergies and trade-offs of agronomic management while accounting for the controlling effects of site-specific factors (covariates). We systematically evaluated 113 meta-analytical studies assessing impacts of crop management measures (rotation, cover cropping, residue retention), soil and water measures (irrigation, tillage), soil amendments (enhanced efficiency, biochar), fertilizer use (organic, mineral, combined organic-mineral) and “4R” fertilizer strategies (right source, rate, timing, placement) on sustainability indicators. These indicators include crop yield, crop N and P (content, uptake, and use efficiency), soil quality indicators (soil organic C, N and P contents, compaction), soil emissions of ammonia (NH₃) and greenhouse gases (CO₂, N₂O), and nutrient losses to water (N and P surplus or leaching). Nutrient management, including 4R practices as well as enhanced efficiency amendments, had the largest impact, increasing crop yields and N uptake while reducing N₂O and NH₃ emissions as well as N surplus, whereas effects on CO₂ emissions were variable. Although all measures positively impacted soil C, the largest effect was due to biochar, followed by organic fertilizer input. Biochar positively impacted crop yield, diminished N₂O and NH₃ emissions as well as N surplus, and increased CO₂ emissions. Within crop management, only cover cropping had a significant positive effect on crop yield, while both cover crops and rotation slightly enhanced N uptake and the sequestration of C and N in soil, thus reducing N₂O emissions and N surplus. Minimal tillage practices generally increased SOC, while results for crop yield, N surplus and N₂O emissions were variable. Site-specific factors had substantial impacts on the evaluated impacts of measures, most importantly climate, crop type, soil texture, soil pH, soil organic C, N dose, and experimental duration. Considering the variation among meta-analytical protocols followed, we recommend that field studies and meta-analytical work adhere to harmonized guidelines with respect to the reporting of site-level data, experimental design, and the statistical procedures used. This will ensure data comparability between studies, improve the quality of meta-analysis results, and give better insights into currently uncertain or unknown impacts of agronomic measures.

1. Introduction

Agricultural activities during the last half century have undoubtedly led to societal tradeoffs, most notable being the large increase in food production in comparison to the various negative effects of intensification (Pretty, 2008). Impacts include biodiversity loss through land conversion and pesticide use (Dudley and Alexander, 2017; Geiger et al., 2010; Tscharncke et al., 2012), eutrophication of water bodies and aquatic ecosystems associated with nutrient loss (Withers et al., 2014), and a large contribution to anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (IPCC, 2019). Soil erosion and deteriorating soil chemical,

biological and physical functions will likely have adverse impacts on crop production on the long term (Lal and Moldenhauer, 1987). Various indicators have been used to measure impacts on soil quality, such as organic matter, nutrient levels and soil compaction (Bünemann et al., 2018). Furthermore, deterioration of soil organic carbon (SOC) levels affects CO₂ emissions as well as buffering capacity against environmental pollutants (Paustian et al., 2016; Stolte et al., 2015), while climate change itself likely poses challenges for the resilience of farming systems (Stevanović et al., 2016; Wiesmeier et al., 2016). Limited resource availability, in particular for phosphorus and some micro-nutrients, further increases the pertinence of smart and sustainable

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intensification of agriculture (Cordell et al., 2009; Sattari et al., 2012).

Many agricultural management practices have been suggested to improve the sustainability of farming and reduce adverse environmental effects. As it becomes increasingly important to control the fate of nutrients in cropping systems, measures that synchronize nutrient supply and crop demand are key to optimizing trade-offs amongst yield, profit, and environmental protection (Cassman et al., 2002; van Groenigen et al., 2011). For example, the "4R" fertilizer strategies (right type, right rate, right timing, right placement) are recommended to improve nutrient (nitrogen and phosphorus) use efficiency (NUE and PUE) (Eagle et al., 2017b; Hopkins and Hansen, 2019). Optimal crop rotation schemes can substantially reduce pesticide use and encourage disease-suppressive soils (Peters et al., 2003), while the inclusion of leguminous or cereal crops in rotation may reduce nitrogen (N) fertilizer use, improve soil structure, enhance soil organic matter and reduce leaching to groundwater (Arriaga et al., 2017; Tonitto et al., 2006). Incorporating organic residues and fertilizers is important for maintaining soil fertility and resilience as well as the supply of micronutrients vital for crop growth (Gómez-Sagasti et al., 2018; Janssen, 2002). Principles of Conservation Agriculture, including maximal soil cover and residue retention, minimal soil disturbance and diversified crop rotation, are known to not only enhance SOC but also reduce soil compaction and stimulate soil biodiversity (Arriaga et al., 2017; Giller et al., 2015; Haddaway et al., 2014; Lugato et al., 2014; Page et al., 2020).

To address the challenge of maintaining crop yields and soil fertility while reducing nutrient losses, best management practices should focus on maximizing NUE, natural resources, and biodiversity rather than solely focusing on yield increases. To this end, understanding the impact of agronomic measures on farm production, soil quality and environmental impacts is crucial for defining strategic pathways to sustainable intensification. Given the high impact of site properties, such as climate, soil properties and crop type, meta-analysis is a valuable way to assess management treatments across agricultural systems (Borenstein et al., 2009; Haddaway and Rytwinski, 2018). The rise in meta analytical studies over the past decade has quantified mean responses of agronomic sustainability indicators to changes in management across regions with varying climates and soil conditions (Eagle et al., 2017a; Gurevitch et al., 2018; Philibert et al., 2012). Key indicators such as crop yield, nutrient (N and P) use efficiency, soil organic carbon (SOC) content, soil nutrient (N and P) content, soil compaction, emissions of C and N to the atmosphere, as well as N and P losses to water have been assessed.

By pulling from existing observational data in field experiments, meta-analysis techniques already eliminate some elements of uncertainty by combining multiple data sources into a single effect size describing management impacts. However, the consensus on overall impacts of management practices, even measured by meta-analysis, is not consistent and strongly depends on the methodology and data selections used. Results among studies can differ greatly in magnitude, may contradict one another, or may indicate trade-offs. For example, although diversifying crop rotations may be important from an environmental and biodiversity perspective, studies have indicated different outcomes for impacts on crop yield, SOC and N surplus (Arriaga et al., 2017; Young et al., 2019). Furthermore, minimal tillage practices generally increase SOC, but most likely at the expense of reduced crop yields (Cooper et al., 2016; Pittelkow et al., 2015; Soane et al., 2012). Clear-cut conclusions on best farm management based on results from single meta-studies therefore remains a challenge. We hypothesize that variation in site-specific factors, including (1) site properties such as climate, soil and crop type, as well as (2) experimental factors such as duration and secondary management practices, are responsible for these differences. For example, van Kessel et al. (2013) find that climate, experimental duration, and fertilizer placement have important effects on the impacts of reduced tillage on nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions and crop yield. Similarly, Han et al. (2016) find that climatic conditions and

crop residue management strongly affect the impacts of fertilizer management on SOC changes. Ignoring these impacts or not properly assessing them in meta-analytical approaches might lead to undesired biases.

In this study, we review agricultural meta-studies and synthesize empirical relationships and meta-analytical models with the aim to: (i) improve the assessment of the impact of an array of management measures on production, soil quality, and the environment; and (ii) evaluate the effect of site-specific factors on the impacts of the measures. This will improve and guide the design of holistic management recommendations considering synergies and trade-offs among agronomic measures. We reviewed studies assessing impacts of crop management measures (rotation, cover cropping, residue retention), soil and water measures (irrigation, tillage), soil amendments (enhanced efficiency products, biochar), fertilizer (organic, mineral, combined effects) and the 4R fertilizer strategies (right source, rate, timing, placement) on production, soil quality and environment. We quantify impacts for the following indicators: crop yield, crop N uptake (estimated via crop N content, N uptake or N use efficiency), crop P uptake (estimated via crop P content, P uptake, or P use efficiency), soil quality (estimated via SOC, N and P contents as well as compaction), greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂, N₂O) and nutrient losses to air (NH₃) and water (via N and P surplus or leaching). The effect of both site properties and experimental factors (the sum of both being defined as site-specific factors) on the impacts of the various measures is investigated but limited to crop yield, SOC, N surplus and N₂O, in response to the main types of measures grouped by cropping diversity, tillage and organic fertilization, which we found to be the most important combinations of measures and impacts. We provide a comprehensive overview of meta-studies covering multiple agroecological zones, management options, and indicators for the sustainability of agriculture, and evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the meta-analytical approaches in order to guide further research.

2. Methodological approach

2.1. Review of meta-analytical studies (qualitative)

We conducted a literature search for meta-analytical studies which were conducted up to and including May 2019 regarding effect sizes for major crop, soil, and environmental indicators in response to management treatments. Search strings were constructed using the online database ISI Web of Science with key words related to crop productivity, soil quality, environmental losses, cropping management, soil management, and fertilization strategy.

The full search terms for impacts included: crop yield, crop N indicators (nitrogen use efficiency, N uptake, or crop N content), crop P indicators (phosphorus use efficiency (PUE), P uptake, or crop P content), soil organic carbon, soil organic nitrogen (SON), soil phosphorus content, soil compaction, soil carbon dioxide emissions (CO₂), soil nitrous oxide emissions (N₂O), soil ammonia emissions (NH₃), nitrogen / nitrate losses in the form of leaching, runoff, or surplus (called N surplus), and phosphorus / phosphate losses in the form of leaching, runoff, or surplus (called P surplus). We organized our analysis based on aggregated groups of indicators, further described in Table 1. For management measures, search terms included: rotation or multi-cropping, cover or catch cropping, legume in rotation, crop residues, irrigation, reduced tillage, no tillage, organic fertilizer, combined fertilizer, fertilizer rate, fertilizer timing, fertilizer placement, enhanced efficiency fertilizer, and biochar. These key words reflect common management practices recommended for agricultural sustainability. We added further meta-studies based on relevant scientific reports and reference lists of meta-analytical literature. A description of included management treatments and controls is presented in Table 2.

Studies were included which linked at least one management practice to one of the aforementioned impacts. When meta-analytical studies were updates of a previous analysis or made use of repeated data, only

Table 1
Description of indicators and variables included in each group (as used in results).

Group name	Variables included
Crop yield	Crop yield, grain yield, crop productivity
Crop N	Nitrogen use efficiency (NUE), N uptake, crop N content
Crop P	Phosphorus use efficiency (PUE), P uptake, crop P content
Soil organic carbon	Soil organic carbon content, soil organic carbon stock, soil organic matter
Soil organic nitrogen	Total organic N
Soil phosphorus	Available P
Soil compaction	Bulk density, aggregate stability
CO ₂ emissions	Soil carbon dioxide emissions
N ₂ O emissions	Soil nitrous oxide emissions
NH ₃ emissions	Soil ammonia emissions
N losses	N surplus, leaching or runoff as dissolved inorganic N, nitrate, or ammonium
P losses	P leaching or runoff

Table 2
Description of management practices.

Management practice name	Treatment description	Control
Rotation or multi-cropping	crop rotation with a second crop type instead of single crop crop diversification by more than two crops in rotation double cropping for multiple crop harvests in one year intercropping to increase number of crops grown simultaneously on one field	monoculture 2 crop rotation / monoculture single cropping monoculture one crop monoculture
Cover crop Legume	cover cropping, catch cropping including a legume in rotation and addition effects of N fixation	no cover crop no legume in rotation
Residue retention	retaining or incorporating crop residues after harvest, mulching	removing
Irrigation	irrigation (not included in quantitative analysis)	rained
Reduced tillage	reduced or minimal tillage practices such as strip till, zone till ridge till, reduced tillage passes, medium intensity non-inversion tillage up to 40 cm depth	conventional tillage*
No tillage	no tillage	conventional tillage*
Nitrogen rate	specific fertilizer rate assessed by levels or continuous data	no fertilizer
Phosphorus rate	specific fertilizer rate assessed by levels or continuous data	no fertilizer
Right fert. organic-mineral**	organic fertilizer, namely from animal waste or compost	mineral fertilizer
Right fert. Combined**	combined organic and mineral fertilizer	mineral fertilizer
Right rate**	improved/optimized or reduced fertilizer rate	conventional rate
Right timing**	improved/optimized timing of fertilizer application	conventional timing
Right placement**	improved/optimized placement of fertilizer	conventional placement
Enhanced efficiency	application of enhanced efficiency fertilizers which are inhibitors of nitrification	not applied
Biochar	application of biochar (most frequent), biofertilizer (not included in quantitative analysis)	not applied

*conventional tillage includes any traditional or full-field tillage operations such as moldboard, chisel plow, disk harrow, high intensity, inversion tillage, or any non-inversion tillage deeper than 40 cm. **4R-defined practices (right type, right amount, rate timing, right placement of fertilizer).

the most recent was selected. Focus was on improved management of arable farming systems including grains, maize and root crops. We did not report effect sizes for baseline practices such as mineral fertilizer rate. For each paper, we also collected information regarding geographic scope, management treatments and impacts covered, data transformation and standardization used, imputation techniques and statistical meta-analysis models used, methods for dealing with data independence, assessment of bias, type of measurements included, duration of management treatment, total number of studies included, total number of paired observations, covariates assessed, and the main method of quantifying covariate influence. This data can be found in the supplementary material.

2.2. Synthesis of effect sizes (quantitative)

We synthesized effect sizes in what may be compared to a “meta-analysis of meta-analyses”. Reported response ratios (a relative change due to a measure) and other estimates of relative change were extracted from meta-analytical studies for all combinations of indicators and management measures in Fig. 1. Estimates of absolute change (such as raw mean difference) were excluded in order to have consistent comparisons in percentage change (most commonly reported). Where estimates from field and laboratory incubation studies were given separately, only data were recorded for field conditions. When laboratory and field measurements were grouped together, effect sizes were excluded if the majority of observations came from laboratory estimates. Recorded effect sizes occasionally included a smaller proportion of greenhouse or lysimeter estimates. Other studies group together various land classes along with arable crops. As long as arable land made up the majority of observations in a meta-study, we included the effect size in our synthesis. The experimental duration was either derived from records in the original studies, or it was estimated based on information given in the publication. By dividing over this value, an average annual effect size was estimated.

Results were aggregated and evaluated for crop yield and nutrient uptake, soil fertility and compaction, and environmental impacts, resulting in a total of 298 recorded effect sizes. When different meta-studies covered the same management-impact pair, we provide averages of the reported effect sizes, weighted by standard error, as described in Young et al. (2020). Different reported measures of variation (e.g. standard deviation, standard error, confidence intervals, and p-values) were converted into a common measure of standard error in order to calculate the weighted mean and compare effect sizes in figures. Due to a lack of information on certain indicators, management, and reporting, some effect sizes were not included in the quantitative part of our study (e.g. irrigation, biofertilizer) or there were a limited number of observations available (e.g. soil P). Because compaction indicators (bulk density and aggregate stability selected) were only found in one study, we used a combined estimate derived from the average change in these two indicators.

The impact of site-specific factors controlling the response to measures was assessed separately. To explore the influence of these covariates, we selected the most frequently reported groupings across a number of studies in order to compare meta-analytical measures among those groups. To have a comparable approach across studies, we extracted effect sizes from the most commonly reported subgroup estimates only and excluded coefficients from regression models due to the limited number. This resulted in 653 recorded effect sizes. We summarized their effects for three management categories, where diverse rotations (category 1) include crop rotation and retention of residues, organic fertilizer (category 2) includes the addition of organic fertilizer sources either alone or combined with mineral fertilizers, and reduced tillage (category 3) includes both no till and reduced till practices. To facilitate an overview of different factors as well as the levels of each factor, the effects of covariates are discussed based on the average response for one level of a factor compared to the mean effect size of all

Fig. 1. Bubble chart of meta-analytical studies for each management practice-impact indicator combination. Each axis intersection in the matrix represents the number of studies reporting an effect size for the corresponding management practice and impact indicator, where the bubbles are proportional to the number of studies. Colors represent the type of impacts: green = crop-related impacts (top), brown = soil impacts (middle), blue = environmental impacts (bottom). Some impact indicators and management practices are displayed as a grouping of several similar indicators or management treatments, a description of which is provided in Tables 1 and 2.

factors reported for each practice. Effect sizes for covariates were more challenging to synthesize due to the fact that measures of variance were often lacking. Therefore, we used sample size as a weight for determining average covariate effects. A summary of indicators and management practices is described in Tables 1 and 2, with further information found in supplementary materials.

3. Review of meta-analytical studies

3.1. Evaluated combinations of management practices and impact indicators

The literature search resulted in 113 relevant meta-studies (summarized in supplementary material) covering a range of management practices, crop, soil quality and environmental impact indicators (Fig. 1), as well as covariates representing site-specific factors. Site properties include environmental variables (e.g. soil, climate, crop type), while experimental factors include secondary management practices applied alongside primary measures (e.g. fertilizer rate) and other properties (e.g. duration of treatment) of the field studies included. The studies are spread over different geographic scopes, including global (70 studies), temperate climate zones (4 studies), tropical climate zones (Africa; 4 studies), Europe-specific regions (Mediterranean, Scandinavia, European regions, and European countries; 15 studies), and country-specific (US, Canada, China; 20 studies).

The most evaluated management practices are organic fertilizer source (33 studies), no tillage (31), followed by crop residue management (17) and enhanced efficiency fertilizers (17), and crop rotation (16), reduced tillage (16), and nitrogen rate (16), and finally cover cropping (14). Legumes, irrigation, phosphorus dose, combined fertilizer, fertilizer placement, fertilizer timing, improved fertilizer dose, and biological soil amendments (including biochar and biofertilizer) were each mentioned in 10 studies or less. Most commonly assessed indicators

include crop yield (45 studies), SOC (36), and soil N₂O emissions (33), followed by N surplus (19) and indicators for crop N uptake, (i.e. crop N content, N uptake and NUE) (19). Other indicators were soil N content (15 studies), soil NH₃ emissions (8), and soil CO₂ emissions (7). Crop P, soil P content, compaction, and P surplus were each reported in four studies or less.

Relationships among management and impacts (Fig. 1) are structurally biased. Crop yield, SOC, and N₂O emissions are frequently studied impacts for all management practices, while the fate of P (crop P, soil P, P losses) and soil compaction are underrepresented. Ammonia is somewhat limited as well in that it is mostly included in studies on optimum fertilizer strategies. Compaction outcomes, although focused on crop rotation, tillage practices, and organic fertilizer effects, are limited in the sense that they are the results of a single study. Frequently studied management measures include no tillage, organic fertilization, and the use of enhanced efficiency fertilizers. Underrepresented measures are irrigation, P fertilizer rate, and legume in rotation. The most commonly assessed measure-impact combinations are the effects of organic fertilizer on SOC (15 studies), no tillage on SOC (14), organic fertilizer on yield (11), no tillage on yield (11), and enhanced efficiency fertilizer on N₂O emissions (10).

3.2. Weighting of individual effect sizes from field studies

Meta-analysis generates estimates of a (weighted) average change in an indicator (an effect size) due to an agronomic measure, the dispersion of these changes, and the homogeneity (or heterogeneity) of the total set of observed effect size. It further supports the exploration of variables controlling the effect size (called potential moderators). Meta-analysis studies vary in methodologies applied to estimate mean effects of agronomic measures on indicators evaluated. These include data imputation techniques as well as methods to estimate the extent of heterogeneity, the presence of publication biases, assumptions of

whether the differences between effect sizes observed in different studies are only due to sampling error or not, and regression techniques to evaluate the impact of moderating variables (Borenstein et al., 2009; Hedges et al., 1999).

Out of the 113 publications, 47 either reported inverse-variance weighting (where weights are assigned to each study) or were assumed to have used this procedure based on the methodological description. From these studies, 15 eliminated observations without reported variances, 19 estimated the missing variance by imputation techniques, and 14 did not report whether missing variance was removed. An unweighted analysis was performed by 33 studies, while 14 did not mention whether their analysis was weighted. Sample size was used as a weight in five studies, and the number of experimental replicates was used in 10 studies. Finally, four studies used some combination of these methods, including replicates, number of sites, experimental duration, or sample size for weighting. The most common reason for either doing an unweighted analysis or for estimating the missing variance was that original field studies did not adequately report the variances of their estimates. Unweighted meta-analysis is not recommended due to the fact that allowing both high- and low-precision studies to contribute equally to the effect size estimation would lead to an unbalanced outcome. While it is crucial that some kind of weighting be used in the analysis, we found that many studies skip the weighting step. This supports the findings of Weir et al. (2018) who concluded that choosing an imputed standard deviation based on the range of available data was generally better than omitting observations.

3.3. Statistical assumptions

Conclusions from meta-analytical assessments strongly depend on the models and assumptions used. By definition, a fixed effects model aims to estimate one “true” underlying effect size which is assumed to be homogenous over all studies, with deviation from this effect size being purely due to sampling error. On the other hand, a random effects model assumes there are different effect sizes among all studies and that the true effect size is actually unknown (Schütz et al., 2018). Random effects models aim to estimate this effect size, which is part of a distribution of different true effect sizes with a mean and estimated variance (Harrer et al., 2019). Random effects takes into account that the single effect size is influenced by the study context, such as variation due to different methods of studies or environmental influences at different sites (Hedges and Vevea, 1998; Schütz et al., 2018), and it includes a second “level” error term describing the between-study variance (Harrer et al., 2019).

For the publications in our review, 31 mention the use of a random effects model, and 11 use random effects for categorical variables (management and environmental covariates). Fixed effects models are mentioned for three studies. Some form of a mixed effects model is used for 27 studies, often with random effects at the study-level or for experimental characteristics, and fixed effects for environmental and management (co)variables. For 29 studies no model is mentioned. The estimation of both within-group and between-group heterogeneity is specified in six studies, while three discuss between-group heterogeneity only. In 20 studies, there were various other modeling techniques mentioned, including linear models, ANOVA, and nonlinear approximations. Finally, a common method for generating model outcomes is a bootstrapping procedure (mentioned by 42 studies) for 95% confidence intervals of means, with 16 studies also reporting bias-corrected confidence intervals.

When multiple observations or treatments are collected from individual studies, observations may be correlated with one another, meaning that the data points are no longer independent. Meta-analysis has been found to possess a multi-level structure, and a three-level model has been recommended to account for this by incorporating multiple levels such as country, within which other levels such as study effect may be nested (Cheung, 2019; Harrer et al., 2019). We found that

this guideline is generally followed by analyses that use study as a random effect to account for the variations in characteristics between individual experiments, while fixed effects is often used for explanatory variables.

3.4. Approaches for assessing the impacts of site-specific factors

Since the impact of agronomic measures are controlled by site properties and experimental factors, a wide range of these site-specific factors have been included in meta-analytical assessments as covariates (Fig. 2). Covariates are variables controlling the relationships between agronomic measures and evaluated impacts. We focused on main factors relating to climate, crop, and soil properties, experimental design, and secondary management applied in addition to the primary measure. The most studied effects are for grain crops (47 studies), fertilizer rate and type (46), soil texture (44), maize crops (36), experimental duration (32), soil pH (26), reference SOC (17), and temperate or tropical climate (16). Other crop, soil, climate, management, and experimental characteristics were each assessed in 15 studies or less. The common approach for assessing their impact was subgrouping (98 studies), where the effect of agronomic measures is quantified for separate groups of observations based on categorical variables. Differences among groups are considered significant when confidence intervals do not overlap. Others (38) use regression analyses to assess how a single variable affects the impact of a measure on crop yield, soil quality or environmental indices. Some studies perform correlation analysis between covariates (12) or report on interactions between variables (11). Fewer studies have a more in depth analysis of covariates, with only 10 studies performing a multiple regression where more than one moderator is included. Most studies use subgrouping combined with some form of (multiple) regression analysis.

4. Synthesis of effect sizes

4.1. Yield and nutrient uptake

Reported annual crop yield changes ranged from −16–21% for the majority of measures (individual means, Fig. 3). Yield was strongly positively affected by the amendments biochar and enhanced efficiency fertilizer, which led to 8.3% and 5.7% increases, respectively, as well as cover cropping (12%), which is associated with the positive effects of legumes as cover crops (Marcillo and Miguez, 2017). Most of the other analyzed measures had a limited effect: the magnitude of changes in yield were 5% or less. Crop rotation had a close to neutral yield effect (−1.9%). Improving fertilizer timing and placement increased yield 4.0% and 5.0%, respectively, while switching from mineral fertilizer to organic or combined mineral and organic each had a −5.0% decrease and 1.9% increase. No tillage had a neutral positive effect of 0.7% and reduced tillage resulted in an overall decline of 4.1% in yield.

Our calculated mean impacts on yield for combined and organic fertilizer (overall increase and decrease, respectively) have substantial uncertainty due to a range of individual effects indicating both positive and negative impacts. However, we find our weighted mean impacts unsurprising since we would expect a more positive effect on yield due to combined sources compared to organic or mineral fertilizer alone. The synergistic effects of adding organic sources to mineral sources are known to maintain both micro- and macro-nutrient supply for crops (Janssen, 2002), as well as improve the efficiency of mineral fertilizer while producing longer-term benefits for soil fertility (TSBF-CIAT, 2009). Furthermore, organic farming is generally associated with the challenge of lower crop yields (Ye et al., 2020b). Although the 4R practice of right fertilizer rate aims to maintain yield while diminishing excess N, treatments mainly entail reductions in mineral fertilizer rates and it is thus not surprising for this to result in an overall decrease in yield. The positive impacts of right fertilizer placement and timing can also be expected, because these measures ensure that the crop receives

Fig. 2. Number of meta-studies which assess the effects of covariates related to various crop, soil, and climate properties, as well as experimental or management characteristics.

Fig. 3. Weighted means of multiple studies reporting on crop yield changes due to management practices. Table 2 specifies the control treatment of each management practice. Weighting is based on the final standard deviation (SD) reported for the effect size in each individual study. Final SD for the weighted means are the minimum and maximum SD values reported by the studies from which the overall mean is derived. Values are in percentage change. C: Crop practices; T: Tillage practices; 4 R: Nutrient management principles of right source, right rate, right place, right time; A: Other soil amendments.

more nutrients in the rooting zone and at the best stages for plant growth. Although our results suggest better outcomes for right fertilizer placement and timing, the range in meta-analytical outcomes for right rate warrants continued investigation into matching fertilizer application to crop needs under local site conditions.

Our results suggest that biochar addition strongly stimulated crop production, which may be related to several factors. First is the availability of other nutrients during the growing season and the added effect of its combination with other fertilizer sources, while another important factor is the positive interaction of biochar with soil properties such as pH or cation exchange capacity, which may stimulate crop yield (Ye et al., 2020a). The effects of biochar on yield must also be considered along with the tendency towards experiments assessing single-dose effects over time scales of up to a few seasons. This time period may not capture potential diminishing effects of biochar over longer periods, such as the reduced weathering effect observed by Spokas, (2013). On the other hand, continued yield effects have been indicated past the 3-year mark following biochar application (Ye et al., 2020a), indicating the need for additional investigations on long-term impacts.

Reduced tillage practices had neutral to negative impacts (significant mean decrease), while no tillage had a slightly positive weighted mean (<1%), but with a larger range of both positive and negative effects than for reduced tillage. Our results indicate that crop yields under no tillage were not significantly different from conventional tillage, the range and uncertainty of which may be related to differences in crop production that strongly affect yields in no-till systems. There is a strong relationship between tillage and crop growth constraints, facilitating adequate rooting conditions, plant emergence, and weed control (Barut and Çelik, 2010; Soane et al., 2012). For example, Weber et al. (2017) found higher weed reduction and crop yields under reduced till, but lower yield under no tillage attributed to poor plant emergence due to technical issues with mulch seeding. In practice, differences between minimal tillage and conventional tillage may be even larger than found in the meta-analyses since minimal tillage is often applied with low or no herbicide use, combined with more diversified crop rotations to reduce weeds (Anderson, 2015; Weber et al., 2017).

Various studies reporting on the crop response to N availability, such as crop N content, N uptake, and NUE, were aggregated into one outcome describing the relative change in crop N (Fig. 4). Crop rotation, cover cropping, and enhanced efficiency fertilizer, as well as right fertilizer timing, rate, and placement show clear positive mean effects, ranging from 7% to 19%. Although crop N impacts of cover cropping (19%) and reduced tillage (−9%) are based on single meta-studies, clear impacts were observed. Residue retention as well as no tillage show

slightly negative mean impacts (−1.7 and −1.3%). Positive impacts on crop N from nutrient addition may be expected, which is in line with observed effects from improved fertilizer application. Although diverse cropping measures have shown advantages for crop yield, it remains unclear as to whether they can be directly linked to improved N supply for crop uptake (Taveira et al., 2020). Although positive effects on nutrient availability and uptake by crops have been reported for minimal tillage systems (Baligar et al., 2001), we do not necessarily find the negative impacts of minimal tillage surprising. Considering that more intensive tillage may provide better short-term plant growth conditions as previously mentioned for crop yield effects, reduced till may lead to less overall nutrient uptake if crop yields are affected. Since we average effect sizes over total treatment durations to convert to annual estimates, it is important to consider that differences in short and long-term effects may be neutralized.

Right source organic as well as combined fertilizer show high-magnitude effects in both the positive and negative direction, leading to a neutral overall mean effect. This could partially be explained by the fact that various types of organic fertilizer were included in our definition of these measures, contributing to varied outcomes. For example, when cattle slurry and farmyard manure replaced mineral sources, estimates were negative (−21 to −11%) while compost had a positive impact (4%). Differences between the treatment and control in various experiments might be due to another reason: whether the control soil has received similar levels of total or effective nutrient doses. Furthermore, the most extreme estimates for organic fertilizer (−32% and 71%) were from the same study, where Gardner and Drinkwater (2009) found a negative effect on crop N recovery in the first growing season after shifting from mineral to organic fertilizer, while they found a positive effect after the second growing season without adding additional nutrients. This contributes to more variation in our estimates and also indicates that multi-year studies are important for better understanding the temporal dynamics of organic N (Gardner and Drinkwater, 2009).

In contrast to crop yield, crop N indicators showed a wider overall range in magnitude for most measures (−32–83% for individual means), with neutral to positive outcomes. This is partially due to the fact that several indicators are bulked together. Our results indicate that NUE may be affected more strongly by measures that decrease overall nutrient losses, while crop N content or uptake may stay relatively constant at adequate fertilizer rates. Right fertilizer rate, for example, shows negative to neutral observations for N content and uptake (−5.6–2.2%), and on the other hand very positive observations for NUE (48–83%). Right fertilizer placement has a similar effect, albeit less pronounced. Enhanced efficiency shows the same trend, with a range of

Fig. 4. Weighted means of multiple studies reporting on crop N indicators (crop N content, crop N uptake, or NUE) changes due to management practices. See Fig. 3 for further explanation.

–0.9–18% for N content or uptake and 12–57% for NUE changes. Enhanced efficiency fertilizers may especially increase NUE by minimizing nitrification until the crop is in its log growth phase (Akiyama et al., 2010), thus providing better timing for crop development. Results also indicate that crop residue addition, crop rotation, and no tillage may also affect NUE more than N uptake. Nkebiwe et al. (2016) was the only study in our review on crop P uptake, reporting increases of 4–19% due to surface banding and subsurface fertilizer placement.

4.2. Soil fertility and compaction

Within the context of this review, soil fertility is assessed given the organic matter and nutrient content of arable soils. Though numerous soil properties and indicators have been researched to assess soil quality (Bünemann et al., 2018; Rinot et al., 2019), meta-analysis techniques were less prominent in agricultural studies until the last decade. Since the relationship between some properties and agronomic measures is not yet common in peer reviewed meta-analysis publications, our soil fertility assessment is limited to the aspects of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus dynamics. Mean SOC responses were overall positive, and all weighted means fell within 0.28–1.3% annual change, with the exception of biochar (27%). Individual effect sizes ranged from –2.3–27% (Fig. 5). SOC changes are typically more pronounced over the long term, making it logical to observe a lower magnitude of annual changes compared to other indicators in this review (e.g. crop yield or N surplus). However, even the smallest changes in SOC can still have relatively large effects on soil functioning and climate change (Goulding et al., 2013).

Biochar has by far the largest impact on carbon content (27%), which is not surprising considering that biochar is made up of more than 65% carbon (Kim et al., 2013). As mentioned for crop yield, the large effect of biochar may also be related to the fact that long-term effects were not captured, since only experiments with very short duration (often less than one season) were included (Liu et al., 2016). Direct additions of organic matter in the form of combined organic-mineral fertilizer as well organic fertilizer alone (1.3% and 1.1%, respectively) were the next most effective at raising SOC levels. Residue management and cover cropping have the next largest annual impacts on soil carbon (0.8% and

0.5%, respectively), which is logical considering the direct addition of carbon through crop residues. In a review synthesis of SOC changes, Bolinder et al. (2020) found similar outcomes, although differences in mean study duration prevented a clear calculation in annual terms. The highest percentage changes were for manure application, followed by crop residue retention and cover cropping (Bolinder et al., 2020), and based on their annual estimates, outcomes would roughly correspond to 1.4%, 0.9%, and 0.5% yr^{-1} , respectively. Our results show overall relatively low reduced and no tillage effects (0.3% and 0.4%) compared to other measures. Although minimal tillage is known for its C sequestration potential (Lal et al., 2011), there are ongoing concerns that reduced tillage may only enrich SOC in surface layers, leading to relatively small differences in the overall soil profile (Krauss et al., 2020). Furthermore, in comparison to practices adding organic matter directly, tillage practices require time to accrue indirect (positive) impacts, which could explain the relatively low annual impact. Crop rotation and reduced fertilizer rate each showed small but positive impacts (0.3%) on SOC.

Numerous measurements of soil N were assessed by meta-studies (total organic N, nitrate, ammonium, dissolved organic N, dissolved inorganic N, and 15 N recovery). The dynamic behavior of inorganic N in soil limits their use for environmental impact assessments (Cardoso et al., 2013) and therefore we focus on total organic N only (Fig. 6). In summary, soil N effects were the highest for crop rotation (1.8%), followed by cover cropping (1.3%) and organic and combined sources (0.9%), while there were neutral effects for reduced tillage (0.6%), residue management (0.1%), and no tillage (–0.3%). Although soil organic N (SON) is a relevant environmental indicator, it is not often the focus of meta-analytical models. Furthermore, there were few data points for soil available P (three meta-studies assessing six measures), with overall positive effect sizes that ranged from 0.37%–6.3% for crop rotation and cover cropping, 4–12% for combined and organic fertilizer, and 0.93–3.8% for reduced and no till practices. Broad conclusions are therefore challenging for both soil N and soil P. However, our results indicate distinct N increases for crop rotation, organic fertilizer, and reduced tillage, as well as distinct P increases for organic and combined fertilizers as well as reduced and no till practices. Overall, positive mean effects were found for almost all measures for soil C, N, and P contents.

Fig. 5. Weighted means of multiple studies reporting on SOC changes due to management practices. See Fig. 3 for further explanation. Due to the large magnitude of biochar impact (27% increase estimated from one study), this effect size is not shown on the range of the graph but indicated with an asterisk (*).

Fig. 6. Weighted means of multiple studies reporting on SON changes due to management practices. See Fig. 3 for further explanation.

Soil compaction indices came from one meta-study, Guzmán et al. (2014), which quantified several indicators of compaction. We combined the estimates for bulk density (increase indicates an undesired change) and aggregate stability (increase indicates desired change) to get a better picture of the effects of measures, reversing the bulk density response so that the positive direction represents desirable changes in either indicator. Organic fertilizer and residue management had the most positive effects (1% and 0.7%), while crop rotation had the most negative effect overall (−0.8%). Reduced tillage practices and cover cropping had close to neutral overall impacts. Especially high means were reported for the individual effect of organic fertilizer on aggregate stability (14%) and the effect of no tillage on aggregate stability (4.8%). Broad conclusions such as found for other indicators are not yet possible for soil compaction.

4.3. Environmental impacts for GHG emissions and nutrient losses

Relatively few studies analyze CO₂ emissions (soil respiration) (Fig. 7), preventing clear-cut conclusions. However, our synthesis indicates enhanced release of CO₂ from soil due to organic fertilizer (36%) and residue management (21%), and small increases due to biochar (5%). There were negative impacts for no tillage (−3%), enhanced efficiency fertilizer (−8%), and reduced tillage (−17%). This generally corresponds to the impact of these measures on SOC: measures which

tend to improve C inputs to the soil also increase the decomposition rate since plant and root material is an essential energy source for soil microbes and fungi (Georgiou et al., 2017; Lal, 2016), while less soil disturbance due to a reduction in tillage operations may reduce emissions.

Outcomes for soil N₂O emissions generally do not show clear positive or negative impacts, with most ranges of individual means overlapping with zero. This is with the exception of the significant 40% decrease due to biochar (Fig. 8). The link between biochar and the N cycle is a current topic of interest, and the ability of biochar to reduce N₂O emissions has been linked to its redox properties (Borchard et al., 2019; Cayuela et al., 2015). However, while most biochar studies have looked at relatively short time periods, there is still a need to better understand how biochar ageing affects its ability to decrease N₂O emissions (Cayuela et al., 2014; Spokas, 2013). As mentioned before, we expect this bias to magnify our measured biochar impacts, and that over longer time periods the impacts may be lower. The various effects of biochar on the N cycle, the importance of biochar production characteristics and application frequency, as well as the soil properties controlling biochar impacts should be taken into account in its use (Liu et al., 2018). N₂O increased due to organic fertilizer (23%), residue management (6%), and no tillage (3%), while there were neutral effects for reduced tillage (1%), right fertilizer timing (−0.26%), and combined fertilizer (−2%). Furthermore there were small decreases in N₂O for crop rotation (−4%), cover cropping

Fig. 7. Weighted means of multiple studies reporting on CO₂ emission changes due to management practices. See Fig. 3 for further explanation.

Fig. 8. Weighted means of multiple studies reporting on N₂O emissions changes due to management. See Fig. 3 for further explanation. An asterisk (*) indicates additional effect sizes included in mean but not shown in range of graph: one for residue retention (241% increase) and one for organic fertilizer (413% increase).

(-5%), and right fertilizer rate (-9%), and large decreases for right fertilizer placement (-15%) and enhanced efficiency (-36%). Although organic fertilizer increased emissions overall, the large range in outcomes (ranging from -12% to 413% change in N₂O) reflects the significant uncertainty related to the variety of organic sources involved (slurry, manure), variation in manure rates between some field studies included, as well as a low number of observations included in the extreme value of 413%. Increased emissions from organic fertilizer have been associated with changes in available C, soil structure, or microbial communities in some studies (Han et al., 2017). N₂O emissions have been associated with (cover) crop residues, especially under aerobic conditions and for residues with a high C:N ratio, although there is considerable uncertainty surrounding the interactions between C decomposition, N mineralization, and soil water content (Badagliacca et al., 2017; Duan et al., 2018; Li et al., 2013). We would expect cover

cropping to exhibit a similar increasing effect on emissions due to the increase in residues. However, there is only one meta-analysis for cover cropping in our estimate. Furthermore, differences in treatment of the crop biomass in spring may contribute to this contrast, as well as the general uncertainties mentioned above. The range in outcomes for enhanced efficiency are related to the various types included, our results showing that nitrification inhibitors reduce emissions more (-48 to -38%) than controlled-release and urease inhibitors (-38-6%). According to Akiyama et al. (2010), nitrification inhibitors may be more effective at targeting pathways for N₂O emissions by delaying nitrification until the crop has grown enough to absorb more nitrate, thus increasing NUE and strongly reducing denitrification. On the other hand, the effectiveness of controlled-release fertilizers may be reduced by poor timing with plant needs. Furthermore, urease inhibitors delay the hydrolysis of urea but may still result in a similar amount of nitrification and denitrification over time if the same amount of urea is eventually transformed into ammonium without being taken up by crops

Fig. 9. Weighted means of multiple studies reporting on NH₃ emissions changes due to management. See Fig. 3 for further explanation.

(Akiyama et al., 2010).

Ammonia emissions (NH_3) show clear decreases (Fig. 9) due to organic fertilizer (-52%), right fertilizer placement (-43%), timing (-32%), and rate (-31%), as well as combined fertilizer (-28%). It is obvious that ammonia emissions can be managed via optimized fertilizer application methods: reducing ammonium levels in the product, dose and during the emission time after application reduce the chance that available ammonium is emitted as ammonia. For that reason, almost all agronomic fertilizer manuals recommend incorporation of manure and ammonia fertilizers into the soil. Enhanced efficiency impacts show a large overall decrease (-28%), although with variation in the positive direction as well. This is due to the differences in types of amendments, but with a trend opposite to that of N_2O emissions. Urease inhibitors and controlled-release fertilizers decreased NH_3 outcomes ranging from -5% to -21% . Our results support that urease inhibitors and controlled-release fertilizers are more effective at reducing NH_3 emissions by reducing soil ammonium concentrations, while nitrification inhibitors are more effective at reducing N_2O emissions (Akiyama et al., 2010; Huang et al., 2016; Saggar et al., 2013).

Although there were relatively few observations for the effects of measures on N surplus (Fig. 10), there was a clear decrease due to organic fertilizer (-43%), right fertilizer rate (-37%), cover cropping (-35%), biochar (-37%), right fertilizer timing (-30%), combined fertilizer (-29%), and residue management (-20%). Enhanced efficiency showed an overall decrease in N surplus (-36%) and no tillage showed an overall but non-significant increase (5%). Most of the organic measures listed have a positive impact on crop yield and also reduce N surplus. Reducing fertilizer dose and timing can minimize the N surplus as long as the crops have sufficient nutrients for crop growth. These results suggest that underlying data and field experiments have been performed under non-limiting circumstances. Surprisingly, adding organic fertilizers also reduce the N surplus even though organic N is typically not directly plant available. We suspect that increasing the proportion of organic sources simultaneously decreases losses of the concentrated mineral N form while providing other benefits to productivity, such as added micronutrients and soil organic matter (Gram et al., 2020). Only one study in our review, Daryanto et al. (2017a), reported an overall reduction in total P loss for both runoff and leaching in response to no tillage, with a pronounced difference between dissolved P (increase) and particulate P (decrease). This precludes a broad discussion of the impact of management practices on P behavior and P loss, indicating the need for more quantitative syntheses on this topic.

4.4. Effects of covariate site-specific factors

Detailed covariate data with respect to site properties (e.g. climate, crop and soil type) and experimental factors (e.g. duration, co-management) are often lacking or do not allow for simple conclusions on site-specific factors, even at a continental level. Various groups of crop types, soil types, or climate types are often defined differently by different authors, making it challenging to compare or harmonize results across studies. Climate zone, for example, is often reported to show little significance in meta-analytical regression models of individual studies, which is most likely related to the wide spatial gradients existing between data points in individual meta-analyses. Climate categories in particular were only able to be compared in the broad sense (e.g. temperate versus tropical, humid versus dry) rather than for more specific zones.

Nevertheless, we are able to make some broad conclusions on the effects of site-specific factors on the overall mean effect of three management practices (cropping diversity, tillage and organic fertilization) on four indicators (crop yield, SOC content, N surplus and N_2O emissions). These outcomes are summarized in Fig. 11, where we present the mean percentage change (of each level of a factor) in relation to the mean effect size over all site types. Site-specific factors (and their levels) include climate type (tropical, subtropical, temperate, dry, or humid), crop type (cereals, maize, or root crops), soil texture type (fine, medium, or coarse), soil organic carbon level (low, medium, or high), soil pH (low, medium, or high), N fertilizer rate (low, moderate, or high), and experimental duration (short, moderate, or long).

4.4.1. Effect on yield

The general variation observed in crop responses to management measures indicates a strong dependence of crop yield on site-specific conditions. The mean effect of diverse cropping on yield over all site-specific factors was 19% , ranging from -3% to 33% for individual site types (Fig. 11a). Cereal effects for diverse cropping were lower than average, while other crops benefitted more from diverse cropping, especially maize. Maize is known to be adaptable and widely spaced, allowing more potential for the adoption of diverse cropping systems that enhance productivity (Maitra et al., 2020). N rate appeared to be negatively correlated with yield impacts, indicating that where crops had a lower level of nutrient addition, diverse cropping resulted in a higher relative yield increase. If we consider that lowly fertilized plots would lead to lower yield overall, the relative increase from improved cropping practices can be expected to be higher than for plots that

Fig. 10. Weighted means of multiple studies reporting on N surplus (N surplus, leaching, or runoff) changes due to management practices. See Fig. 3 for further explanation.

Fig. 11. Mean effects of a measure (dots) as affected by site-specific factors in comparison to the overall mean impact (solid line). Dotted lines represent the zero effect, indicating no change or a change in effect between negative and positive. Effect sizes were averaged over three main types of management and means were weighted by number of observations. Diverse cropping includes: crop rotation, crop residue retention, and cover cropping; Minimal tillage includes: reduced tillage and no tillage; Organic fertilizer includes: organic fertilizer and combined fertilizer. Green indicates ecosystem-related properties climate or crop, brown indicates soil properties, and blue indicates management-related factors. The impact of diverse cropping on N₂O emissions under fine soil texture (130% increase) is not displayed, indicated by an asterisk (*).

receive adequate nutrients. Yield changes were lower than average for medium compared to coarse and fine soil textures, indicating that diverse cropping performed better on sand and clay. Diverse crop rotations have often been found to improve crop yields on poorly drained clay soils (Dick and Van Doren, 1985; Tran Ba et al., 2016). Other factors such as climate and experimental duration had no clear impact on the effect of diverse cropping on yield.

Minimal tillage effects on yield ranged from -15 – 12% under different site-specific factors, with a slightly positive overall effect of less than 1% (Fig. 11a). Yield increased strongly due to minimal tillage in a dry climate, especially compared to the same practices in tropical zones, for which yield decreased strongly. Minimizing tillage has been found to improve soil structure as well as water availability for crops (Busari et al., 2015), an effect that would be especially pronounced in dry climates and could improve crop growth. Our results on dry and tropical climates were each from single meta-studies on no-till, each concluding that (1) better performance was found in dry climates, especially for rain-fed barley, and (2) barriers limiting the productivity of no-till systems appear to be greatest in the tropics (Huang et al., 2018; Pittelkow et al., 2015). Although the differences are small, minimal tillage had a more negative yield impact for coarse and fine soils than for medium textured soils. This might indicate that on loamy soils, which often have more ideal soil structure for crop growth (FAO, 1995), the detrimental effects of minimal tillage on yield may be less. Yield decreased for acidic soils but increased on alkaline soils under minimal tillage. This reflects the general observation that poor soil pH negatively affects crop yield regardless of the measures discussed here, particularly in extremely acidic soils. Minimal tillage had a slightly more positive effect in long-term experiments, indicating the underlying benefits of discontinuing intensive tillage over the long term (Rusinamhodzi et al., 2011; West and Post, 2002). Finally, cereal yields benefitted strongly from minimal tillage while maize and root crop yields were lower.

The effect of replacing all or part of mineral fertilizer with organic fertilizer sources has an overall slightly negative mean effect on crop yield ($<1\%$), with effects ranging from -11 – 12% under various site-specific factors (Fig. 11a). Yield decreased more than average due to organic sources in temperate and humid climates but increased for subtropical and tropical climates. Cool or wet climates tend to have an elevated level of soil organic matter, which indicates that replacing the concentrated nutrients in mineral fertilizer with organic sources may be less beneficial for crops compared to other climates. Adding organic sources had slightly negative impacts on the short term, indicating that shifting agricultural systems to elevated organic fertilizer use might show benefits on the long term. Organic fertilization had the largest positive effect on yield in neutral pH soils, which generally offers better conditions for crops and nutrient uptake. There was a slightly positive effect in alkaline soils and slightly negative effect in acidic soils, which can be related to several phenomena. At high or low pH, most micronutrients and even some macronutrients are less available. Organic fertilizer is a direct source of nutrients and also adds organic matter, which can help buffer soil pH closer to neutral (McCauley et al., 2017). Although the effect is small, N rate had a positive correlation with yield increase.

4.4.2. Effect on soil organic carbon content

Diverse cropping increased SOC by ($<1\%$) on average, and effects ranged from -0.2 – 1.4% under different site-specific factors (Fig. 11b). Cropping measures were especially positive on coarse and fine textured soils. Sand and clay soils generally tend to have less initial organic matter as well as drainage issues compared to porous and more fertile loamy soils (FAO, 1995), and sand is generally negatively correlated with SOC content (Augustin and Cihacek, 2016). Therefore, recommended measures such as diverse rotations may be expected to improve SOC where initial content is low. The higher degree of physical and chemical protection of carbon by clay particles (Hassink and Whitmore, 1997) may partially explain large increases in SOC under these

conditions. There is furthermore evidence for multiple benefits of diverse cropping on clay soils, including an increase in SOC (Tran Ba et al., 2016). The rooting systems of certain cover crops are also better at loosening compacted clay soils as well as recycling nutrients from deeper layers, thus contributing to increased recovery of organic matter (Rosolem et al., 2002). On average, diverse cropping seemed to have a more neutral impact on SOC in dry climates, compared to slightly lower than average impacts in other climates, especially for temperate zones. This further supports the conclusion that diverse cropping is more beneficial on soils in dryer, warmer climates where lower initial organic matter content may be expected (Plante and Conant, 2014).

The average impact of minimal tillage on soil carbon was small but overall positive ($<1\%$ increase) and although it was affected by site-specific factors, mean impacts for all factors were less than 2.5% (Fig. 11b). It seemed that minimal tillage practices resulted in a higher SOC increase for coarse and fine textured soils and a below-average impact for medium textured soils. This matches our findings for diverse cropping, underpinning the conclusion that yield and SOC changes are complementary to each other, and that there is more potential for SOC increases in sandy soils with low organic matter and moisture content. Conservation tillage generally improves water content, increases plant residue inputs, and regulates soil temperature; furthermore, it may improve infiltration in sandy soils (Busari et al., 2015). SOM decomposition rates are also maximized at intermediate soil moisture levels, which may partially explain the less-pronounced effect in loamy soils (Plante and Conant, 2014). The impact of minimal tillage on SOC with maize as the main crop was especially high (more than double the mean effect). Although this is different for what we found for yield (higher increase for cereals than maize), it may be that soils cropped with cereals have better residual soil carbon initially. Although studies have indicated that cereal yield may improve under diverse crop rotations, tillage practices may have less of a determining influence (Agomoh et al., 2020; Woźniak, 2020).

Adding organic fertilizer to soils positively impacted SOC (1.8%) and showed increases from 0.34 – 2.9% depending on site effects (Fig. 11b). There were above-average impacts for tropical and humid climates compared with below-average impacts for temperate and subtropical climates. This might reflect the fact that initial soil organic carbon levels may be lower in warmer or wetter climates due to increased decomposition rates (Plante and Conant, 2014). Less frequent addition of organic matter (short duration) resulted in much lower SOC mean change (close to zero) compared to longer durations, which may indicate better impacts of organically-sourced nutrients on SOC over the long term.

4.4.3. Effect on nitrogen surplus and nitrous oxide emissions

Diversification of the cropping system generally resulted in a decline in N surplus (-51%) with small variation (-65 to -38%) in the mean effect for various site-specific factors (Fig. 11c). Crop diversification had a slightly higher N surplus in clay soils, which decreased slightly with medium and coarse texture. N surplus was also especially diminished under low initial SOC status. We would expect N surpluses to decline due to the inclusion of cereals and other deep rooting crops that make efficient use of soil available nitrogen, in particular on sandy soils with low nutrient and water holding capacity. Coarse or light soils tend to have more nutrient losses due to leaching, and one study found that adding up to 20% clay to sandy soil resulted in 83% more soil N retention and a doubling of soil P retention (Tahir and Marschner, 2017). As a consequence, we conclude that the relative N losses to ground and surface water may be more positively affected by crop diversification under relatively higher soil sand content.

All observations for minimal tillage and N surplus under site-specific factors came from one study, Daryanto et al. (2017b), which measured the effects of no tillage on nitrate concentration in runoff and leaching. Minimal tillage had a slightly positive effect on N concentrations in leaching and runoff overall (5.7%), ranging from -1.7 – 40% (Fig. 11c). No tillage increased N surplus strongly under cereals compared to maize.

Although unexpected because maize usually requires higher N fertilization than wheat, the authors attribute the higher wheat N surplus to characteristics of winter wheat cultivation, specifically the time gap between fertilizer application and growth period as well as the downward movement of residual soil nitrate upon soil thawing (Daryanto et al., 2017b). Furthermore, differences in reduced and no tillage systems have reported, such as higher maize root mass under reduced compared to no tillage that may be associated with the compact soil surface that can occur under no tillage (Busari et al., 2015). Lal (1993) describe the level of complexity of the effects of different tillage systems, which can lead to various or unexpected outcomes depending on local conditions. As for soil type, no tillage was found most effective for medium-textured soils and the least effective for fine-textured soils, which was attributed to better water infiltration from increased organic matter as well as the absence of surface sealing typical for clay soils (Daryanto et al., 2017b). The overall N surplus increase under minimal tillage over the short term was higher than average, while there was almost zero effect over the long term, indicating better effects of conservation tillage practices when applied over longer time periods. In conclusion, we emphasize that more data is needed, especially as there is not information on reduced tillage systems in this particular instance, to be able to come to better conclusions. There was furthermore not enough data available to estimate the impact of covariates on the effect of organic fertilizer for N surplus, with only one estimate of a 27% decrease under cereal cropping.

Diverse cropping generally had a positive effect on N₂O emissions (21%), but with a wider range of -5.4–130% change under different site-specific factors (Fig. 11d). The mean increase almost doubled for temperate climates while it decreased slightly for subtropical climates and was reduced by almost half for subtropical climates. This indicates that diverse cropping may lead to more mitigation of N₂O release under higher temperatures or precipitation, where positive emissions feedbacks are expected (Griffis et al., 2017). The change in emissions slightly increased for short-term compared to medium-term experimental duration, under which N₂O emissions were reduced. N₂O is highly dynamic over time, and considering that studies evaluating it on the short term are more likely to be affected by variable “events” (e.g. fertilization, precipitation effects, etc.), we conclude that short- and long-term effects may be very different on average and that more long-term studies are needed. Our results indicate a strong N₂O increase under fine texture (130%) compared to other soil types, although this mean was influenced by extreme effect sizes from relatively few observations, indicating uncertainty. Clay soils have been found to have more N₂O emissions in general, which may be related to smaller amounts of macropores increasing anaerobic microsites (Signor et al., 2013). It is important to note that our estimates bulked together crop residue addition along with crop rotation and cover cropping. Crop residue addition can lead to large increases in N₂O compared to other measures, as mentioned in the previous Section (6% increase due to residue addition, and on the other hand 3% and 5% decreases due to crop rotation and cover cropping). Our analysis on diverse cropping effects for N₂O emissions is therefore biased towards the stimulating effects of residue additions.

Minimal tillage has an overall increasing effect of 12% on N₂O emissions, ranging from -1.5–74% under different site-specific factors (Fig. 11d). Emissions were much higher under tropical climates and slightly higher for subtropical zones, while under minimal tillage in temperate climates emissions decreased to almost zero. The effect of the tropical climate is generally the opposite of the outcomes explained previously for crop yield (lower yield under minimal tillage in a tropical climate). This indicates a potential link between lower crop yield (and thus nutrient uptake) and increased pathways for N loss in the form of emissions. Bare soil surfaces have been found to result in much greater N₂O emissions (Oertel et al., 2016) and have been reported to emit 34 times more N₂O during the growing season than soils under barley cultivation (Maljanen et al., 2004). Not surprisingly, mean N₂O

emissions were lower under minimal tillage when less N was applied. Any fertilizer addition containing N increases the input of N to the soil and the chance for losses, fertilizers having majorly influenced soil N₂O emissions (Shakoor et al., 2018). The average effect was also lower for neutral to basic soil pH, while it increased for acidic soils. In acidic soils, N₂O emissions are often greater because N₂O is the main product of denitrification (Signor et al., 2013), which is in line with our results. The mean minimal tillage effect for emissions was lower than average under medium and coarse soil texture, while for fine texture it was higher. Under wet conditions, clay soils are particularly at risk for N₂O emissions following fertilizer additions, which may contribute to a higher effect under fine-textured soils (Velthof and Rietra, 2018).

Organic fertilizer practices have a positive effect on N₂O over all covariate groups (31%), ranging from -14–65% for different site-specific factors (Fig. 11d). There was an especially pronounced positive effect in temperate climates and a negative effect for tropical climates, under which emissions were actually reduced. As mentioned before, under a tropical climate, we would generally expect a higher level of N₂O emissions along with higher temperatures and precipitation (Griffis et al., 2017). Due to less concentrated applications of N in organic fertilizer sources, we would expect a decrease in N₂O release, especially in climates with more risk for soil emissions. Some studies have confirmed a decrease in emissions from the application of organic materials, although the overall effects remain unclear, especially on the long-term (Lv et al., 2020). Low soil pH and longer duration of fertilizer addition also showed above-average effects compared to other groups, which is in line with the results and reasoning we had for the outcomes of minimal tillage. Organic fertilizer addition on medium-textured soils increased N₂O emissions almost twice as much as on average, while for fine texture the mean effect was half that of the average and for coarse texture emissions were reduced strongly. Less risk for N₂O emissions is expected in dry conditions (Velthof and Rietra, 2018), which may explain the especially decreased emissions from organic fertilizer on sandy soils.

5. Conclusion and outlook

5.1. Conclusions on management impacts

Meta-analysis is a powerful statistical tool that has been frequently used for agricultural field data, especially in the last decade. These outcomes can be integrated into applications such as farm management tools, modeling tools simulating management outcomes over geographic regions, or decision support systems that aim for policy recommendations. In view of the relevance for integrative assessments, we reviewed 113 meta-analyses and synthesized 951 reported effect sizes for various impacts of crop, nutrient, and soil management practices on crop, soil, and environmental indicators. This allows a clear picture of: (i) the focus of the evaluated agronomic measures and related indicators, (ii) the effect sizes of the measures for these indicators and (iii) the impacts of site-specific factors, as discussed in this order below.

We found that existing meta-analyses were highly focused on temperate regions, with relatively little attention to tropical areas. In general, the most frequently investigated practices are the use of enhanced efficiency fertilizers and biochar, followed by tillage and crop management. The most frequently studied sustainability indicators are crop yield, SOC sequestration and N₂O emissions followed by crop N, soil N and N losses. Data on crop P, soil P and NH₃ emissions are limited.

Crop rotation generally increased SOC sequestration, crop N, and soil N contents and reduced N₂O emissions, although all impacts were relatively small. Residue retention had similarly low effects, but increased SOC as well as CO₂ and N₂O emissions and especially decreased N surplus. Cover cropping increased crop yield, crop N, SOC, and soil N slightly, while it decreased N₂O slightly and decreased N surplus strongly. In summary, crop management generally slightly enhances N uptake and the sequestration of C and N in soil, thus reducing

N₂O emissions and N surplus.

Enhanced efficiency amendments increased crop yield and crop N, while reducing CO₂, N₂O, and NH₃ emissions as well as N surplus. N inhibitors were more effective in reducing N₂O emissions while urease inhibitors and controlled-release fertilizers were more effective in reducing NH₃ emissions. Biochar had a positive impacts on crop yield and SOC (significant increases) as well as N₂O emissions, N surplus (significant decreases), and NH₃ emissions (decrease). 4R strategies generally positively impacted crop yield (except for reduced rate), crop N (except for organic fertilizer), and SOC (increases), as well as N₂O emissions (decreases), while 4R significantly reduced NH₃ emissions and N surplus. Replacing mineral fertilizer with organic sources increased SOC and resulted in large reductions in N loss via NH₃ and N surplus.

Minimal tillage practices had small or varying effects, but generally decreased crop N and increased SOC, while results for N surplus and N₂O emissions were uncertain but indicate an increase. Surprisingly, reduced tillage clearly decreased yield while the impact of no tillage was highly variable with an overall positive weighted mean. No tillage and reduced tillage decreased soil CO₂ release. The overall small magnitude of effects for crop and tillage measures is also related to the large variation of outcomes of meta-analyses, implying that a calculated weighted mean resulted in overall small effects. Conversely, a high number of short-term studies (as for biochar) is likely to result in an abnormally high effect size, which we expect may diminish over time, especially if amendments are not applied every year.

The most frequent approach to assessing site properties and experimental factors as covariates was to estimate distinct effect sizes from subdivided groups of observations. Other studies used multiple regression, but very few integrated more than one covariate into their analysis. The most frequently studied site-specific factors included climate zone, soil texture, soil pH, crop type, N dose, and experimental duration. Although it is difficult to generalize, due to the wide range of indicators and management practices included, and the low significance regarding the impacts on some indicators, we were able to discern some trends.

Results on climate and soil effects are most likely related to improvements in initially poor soil structure, organic matter and water retention. Minimal tillage increased yield more under dry climates, while SOC increased more under organic fertilization in tropical and humid climates, as well as under diverse cropping in dry climates. Both crop yield and SOC benefited more from diverse cropping on coarse- and fine-textured soils. Diverse cropping reduced N surplus slightly more in coarser soil textures, which may be explained by improved crop rooting and thus better nutrient retention in soils with initially low capacity for retaining N. N surplus decreased due to minimal tillage in coarse and fine soil texture and under low SOC status. Especially large reductions in N₂O emissions under diverse cropping in warmer climates may be related to the mitigation of known positive feedbacks in these areas. Minimal tillage seemed to increase N₂O for tropical climates. The larger N₂O emissions found here under diverse cropping and minimal tillage in clay soils has also been confirmed by other studies. Organic fertilization increased N₂O more in medium-textured soils compared to sandy conditions, probably due to differences in moisture. Our findings also highlight the importance of soil pH for crop production and emissions. Crop yield was higher under minimal tillage in loamy and alkaline soils, indicating that better initial cropping conditions of these soils are able to be maintained under reduced tillage. When organic fertilizer replaced mineral fertilizer, yield increased in alkaline soil conditions and tropical climates, which may be related to lower initial availability of nutrients and organic matter. In acidic soils, where N₂O is expected to be the main product of denitrification, emissions increased under minimal tillage and organic fertilizer.

The effect of site-specific factors such as crop type, N rate, and duration of treatments can vary with the management measure that is applied. Maize yields benefitted more from diverse cropping than cereals and root crops, and under minimal tillage, SOC seemed to increase the most when maize was the main crop. N surplus increased strongly

under minimal tillage for cereals compared to maize, although cereal yields benefitted more from minimal tillage. This is unexpected since the deep rooting of cereals and increased growth typically makes better use of soil nitrogen but may be related to differences in winter versus summer wheat cultivation. Diverse cropping increased crop yield more when crops had a lower level of N fertilizer, indicating greater relative impacts of these measures when initial productivity was lower. On the other hand, the amount of N applied as added organic fertilizer had a small but positive correlation with yield increase. N emissions, however, also increased under minimal tillage at high N rate. Long-term treatments frequently showed more positive impacts compared to the short-term, highlighting the crucial aspect of experimental duration for interpreting results of field studies and making management recommendations.

5.2. Lessons learned for meta-analytical studies

We found several important limitations in current meta-analytical studies, limiting their current applications. This refers mainly to (i) limited reporting on experimental design and analysis of variance, (ii) missing information on site-specific factors affecting the impacts, and (iii) conflicting results between studies. First, there is often a lack of reporting on key information on experiments and statistical procedures used. For example, some studies did not clearly state the (average) time frame or number of replicates for which effect sizes were calculated. Furthermore, crucial information on the weighting procedure or statistical assumptions was left out by some studies. A weighted meta-analysis should be used, with an estimation of missing variance values where possible. The use of a hierarchical structure by many studies, as well as the significant effects of site-level characteristics (environmental, management, and study-specific) indicate that some form of a multi-level model structure including random effects is needed for quantifying agronomic impacts. Since the assumptions underlying the fixed effects model approach are rarely met, it is strongly recommended to use a random effects model and to interpret the heterogeneity measures before deciding to use a fixed effects model.

Second, we found a lack of comparable covariate data affecting the effect sizes, including site properties and experimental factors. Furthermore, authors sometimes test many covariates for significance, but if found to be insignificant, they do not report this at all, while this can be an important starting point for future research. Further inconsistencies in reporting made it difficult to adequately illustrate a broad picture of covariates in this review. To unravel site-specific effects and their interactions in the agricultural system, multiple regression analysis of these factors is important. We recommend that new analyses first focus on testing the variables discussed here for potential moderating effects on measures as well as the potential for integration into multi-variate analysis.

Third, our attempt to combine effect sizes from different meta-studies showed clearly conflicting results between different studies, often having varying magnitudes of positive or negative impact. This indicates that for many measures, there is still no clear agreement as to whether they tend to have a positive or negative effect on sustainable intensification of agriculture, or whether there are trade-offs or synergies when considering multiple indicators. It also indicates that further investigation is needed into the influence of site properties on the variation in these estimates. We recognize that our second and third points are constrained by the sample size of a meta-analysis, which is generally limited to the selection of field studies. Collecting data from field experiments to integrate into a meta-analysis is not only a time-consuming process, but the robustness of results is also limited if there is little empirical data available.

The challenges above can at least partially be addressed by integrating additional field-level information. Furthermore, there is the need for more coherent, standardized reporting on experimental design and statistical approaches used, as other studies have also highlighted

(Bolinder et al., 2020; Eagle et al., 2017a; Haddaway and Rytwinski, 2018; Krupnik et al., 2019; Philibert et al., 2012). To reduce the limitations of synthesizing empirical data by means of meta-analysis, it is crucial that individual field studies clearly report on the variance of their measurements, number of replicates, experimental duration and other site-specific factors. Furthermore, we recommend that authors include as much description of the data evaluation procedures used in meta-analytical models to ensure that the quality of results can be verified. This would better allow for (1) critical evaluation of results as well as (2) comparability of results between field studies and among meta-studies. Data sharing as well as consistency in reporting by field and meta-analytical studies is key for future holistic evaluations of the impact of management practices on agronomic and environmental performance indicators.

5.3. Outlook

Apart from improved assessments of the impacts presented here, there is continued potential for future meta-studies or syntheses on other relevant sustainability indicators as more field studies become available. In this study we only included indicators for soil chemical quality due to its strong relationship with crop yield, nutrient losses, and emissions to air, but biological soil quality and other aspects of the agroecosystem should not be overlooked. Soil biological indicators, such as microbial biomass for example, are important for soil health, biodiversity, and long-term crop cultivation (McDaniel et al., 2014). There is further potential in agronomy for the integration of indicators and management measures across various scales. Beyond traditional field studies, advancements in on-farm sensor technology, precision farming, 'big data' integration, and engagement with land users may be coupled with meta-analysis work to validate models and make scientific results accessible to and reliable for stakeholders (Paustian et al., 2016). Studies have demonstrated that integrating meta-analytical data into a decision-support framework can be used to illustrate differences in management under various soil and climate conditions in Europe (Olesen et al., 2016; Young et al., 2020).

This study is meant as a resource for organized information on the state of agronomic meta-analysis, by summarizing many meta-analytical studies that each dive deeply into separate aspects of the agricultural system. Our overview of the impacts of management practices on crop, soil, and environmental quality provides the range of reported effect sizes for each measure and indicator using comparable units. We synthesized this data with the prospect of applying it in a decision support system that develops farm or policy advice based on an integrated assessment of the above-mentioned impacts. We see a clear opportunity for future work to not only generate high quality field data and meta-analytical studies, but also to encourage data sharing and collaboration that drive recommendations for sustainable agroecosystems.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.agee.2021.107551](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107551).

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